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Two photons everywhere

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We discuss two-photon physics, taking for illustration the particular but topical case of resonance fluorescence. We show that the basic concepts of interferences and correlations provide at the two-photon level an independent and drastically different picture than at the one-photon level, with landscapes of correlations that reveal various processes by spanning over all the possible frequencies at which the system can emit. Such landscapes typically present lines of photon bunching and circles of antibunching. The theoretical edifice to account for these features rests on two pillars: i) a theory of frequency-resolved photon correlations and ii) admixing classical and quantum fields. While experimental efforts have been to date concentrated on correlations between spectral peaks, strong correlations exist between photons emitted away from the peaks, which are accessible only through multiphoton observables. These could be exploited for both fundamental understanding of quantum-optical processes as well as applications by harnessing these unsuspected resources.

1. Introduction

Quantum mechanics is notorious for its quantized spectral lines. This is how the theory was born and the fact after which it is named, following Bohr [1]'s quantization of angular momentum of the electron orbitals. This produced Rydberg's constant as a product of fundamental constants and explained the lines as

Figure 1. (a) Old quantum mechanics: transitions between quantized orbitals of the electron lead to a quantized spectrum. Transitions to $n = 2$ form the visible (Balmer) series. The $2 \rightarrow 1$ (Lyman) is in the ultraviolet. The $2s \rightarrow 1s$ is furthermore dipole forbidden, but it can occur with a continuum of two-photon emission, which falls again in the visible range. (b) Transitions between dressed states $|\pm\rangle$ lead to a triplet spectrum (Mollow). A two-photon, so-called *leapfrog*, transition can also occur that jumps over an intermediate state. However weak is this transition, it can be revealed by two-photon correlations. (c) In the low-driving limit, detuning makes the same physics take another turn, with the triplet now formed by the Rayleigh scattering as the central peak and (d) breaking the leapfrog over one real-state transition but keeping the other virtual, accounting for the two side peaks. This results in a rich two-photon physics beyond the side peaks, not visible in photoluminescence but revealed in the two-photon correlation spectrum.

transitions between energy levels (Fig. 1(a)). At about the same time, a much less resounding finding was recorded in a bulletin of the Lowell Observatory: a nebula in the Pleiades was observed to have a completely continuous spectrum of emission [2]. There are many ways to produce a continuous spectrum, from unbound charges to, as was the case here, scattering from a broad spectrum (the light from the star Merope). Systematic and careful observations revealed that emission nebulae (in particular planetary nebulae) which do not reflect but emit light directly, also feature a continuous spectrum in addition to the spectral lines of what was by then well-established quantum theory [3]. One part—the Balmer continuum—could be explained with the known mechanisms from reflection nebulae, but on the other side of the Balmer limit, sitting with the quantized spectral lines in the visible spectrum, lied a continuum spectrum which was of unknown origin [4]. This got simultaneously and independently resolved in 1950, from both sides of the iron curtain [5,6], as a fitting companion to Bohr’s model of quantum jumps in the form of a two-photon emission from the metastable $2S_{1/2}$ shell of the hydrogen atom down to the ground state $1S_{1/2}$ (Fig. 1(a)). Would the atom be excited in the $2P$ level, it would undergo a normal, “Bohrian” transition back to the ground state, but the $2S-1S$ is dipole forbidden so it has to go through the next (quadrupole) order, which is however very weak, and, in ambient conditions, is knocked-off by collision back into a radiative state. In the extremely rarefied cosmic conditions, however, there is plenty of space as well as enough time to have isolated Hydrogen atoms left stuck in great quantity in their $2S$ state. For those, the next best route back to $1S$ is the “Doppelemission” (double-emission or two-photon emission) theorized by Goeppert Mayer [7] and first applied to Hydrogen by Breit and Teller [8]. Although a higher-order process, it is not dipole forbidden and finds in outer space the ideal quiet laboratory conditions making possible its direct observation, indeed giving it the name of “visual continuum”. The Earth-based laboratory is less auspicious for a direct (visual) observation of two-photon emission [9] but the process

nevertheless opened the multiphoton page of atomic physics [10]. Such two-photon transitions have, among other things, be generalized to link any (n, l, m) states of the atom [11] and can be stimulated with a laser [12]. In the solid state, the opposite regime of the interstellar one can be realized of high populations in small volumes, e.g., in semiconductors, where delocalized electrons in the crystal under high laser excitation can jump the bandgap in sufficient amount to produce a measurable and even controllable two-photon continuous spectrum [13]. Another solid-state approach is to inflate the light-matter coupling by focusing light onto the emitter, to make higher-order processes “less smaller” and thus lift their “forbidden” character, possibly making them even comparable to first-order processes [14].

Here, we present a quantum optical alternative to the QED description. The latter typically relies on a perturbative treatment of the two-photon processes of a complex system: the Hydrogen atom in its simplest case, up to an interstellar ionized gas bathed in the radiation of other astronomical objects. Instead, we consider the *exact* treatment of a *simple* system, namely, resonance fluorescence, i.e., the photon emission (fluorescence) of a two-level system driven at the same energy as it is excited (resonance). This will allow us to focus on the two-photon physics itself, instead of interesting but secondary problems specific to Hydrogen or to the thermodynamics of nebulae. While we invoke a variety of our results collected over the last decade, we try to keep the discussion self-contained with no need of prior familiarity with our earlier works on, mainly, frequency-resolved multiphoton correlations [15] or multiphoton interferences of quantum fields [16]. We furthermore connect these two aspects to provide a new and fairly comprehensive picture of the phenomenology of two-photon emission from resonance fluorescence, explaining features hitherto only observed. Section 2 introduces the textbook problem of resonance fluorescence but revisited with the “sensor formalism” [15], which is an alternative way to compute spectra that will allow us, in Section 3, to provide a first departure from conventional treatments, by introducing our concept of frequency-resolved correlations, which will put the two-photon observables on the same footing as the one-photon ones, and explain the reason for our title of “two photons everywhere”. In Section 4, we introduce the other pillar of our edifice: interferences of quantum fields, as underpinning their statistical properties [16]. The basic idea, that holds with quantum states, is applied to a dynamical system in Section 5, which, in spirit, is resonance fluorescence itself, but we show that the two-photon observables are actually captured by the simpler case of a squeezed cavity, allowing us to identify what is specific to quantum states admixtures of Gaussian states (squeezing and coherent states) and what is to the “more quantum” two-level system, to which we return in Section 6 with a focus on detuning. We provide a surprisingly compact expression for two-photon correlations in this case, that is exact to leading order in the driving and captures its main phenomenology. In Section 7, we show how our approach gives way to countless variations, even if remaining at the level of resonance fluorescence, although this could and should be extended to all possible quantum emitters. Specifically, we consider entanglement and other quantum resources such as two-mode squeezing, which we merely exhibit but that could be similarly explained and exploited. Our approach could also usefully revisit closely related problems such as two-photon absorption [17], two-photon resonance fluorescence [18] or two-photon gain [19].

2. Resonance Fluorescence

Resonance fluorescence is the simplest problem of quantum optics, yet a still actively investigated one. Its Hamiltonian in the rotating frame of the laser is (with $\hbar = 1$)

$$H_\sigma \equiv \Delta_\sigma \sigma^\dagger \sigma + \Omega_\sigma (\sigma^\dagger + \sigma) \quad (2.1)$$

where σ is the annihilation operator of a two-level system driven coherently by a laser with amplitude $\Omega_\sigma \in \mathbb{R}$, and Δ_σ is the detuning from the laser frequency ω_L which we shall take as the reference, i.e. $\omega_L = 0$. This problem provides a rich quantum-optical playground, from essentially two regimes of excitation: at low-driving (so-called Heitler regime [20]), the spectrum is dominated by the Rayleigh-scattered light of the laser, while at high-driving (so-called Mollow

regime [21]), there is a splitting of the spectral shape into a triplet (Fig. 1). While these two regimes are very different in character, we can find a first unifying theme through large detuning. When the laser drives the system far from its resonance frequency (although still referring to “resonance fluorescence”), the spectral response remains a symmetric triplet. This is shown at the top of Fig. 2 for (a) the Mollow triplet at resonance, (b) the detuned Mollow triplet with an increasingly bright coherent peak sitting on top of a dim fluorescent one and (c) the detuned (Heitler regime of) resonance fluorescence with vanishing fluorescent contributions. The driving Ω_σ has been chosen so that the spectral position of the side peaks is the same in units of the Mollow splitting $\Omega_+ \approx \sqrt{\Delta_\sigma^2 + 4\Omega_\sigma^2}$ (at large enough detunings). The frequency ω is normalized to this splitting, i.e., $\varpi \equiv (\omega - \omega_L)/\Omega_+$. The central peak is either (a) a fluorescent (broad) peak, (c) the Rayleigh-scattered coherent peak (intense and narrow central peak, note that the side peaks are magnified by a factor 800) or (b) an admixture of a fluorescent and coherent peaks.

One can conveniently derive such results with our sensor formalism [15], which is an alternative to formal results that rely on mathematical structures of the problem—such as the quantum regression theorem or the Wiener-Khinchin theorem—to obtain instead observables from a physical modeling of what is being measured. This was developed to extend the physical spectrum of Eberly and Wódkiewicz [22] to N -photon observables, which instead of computing awkward multi-time, normally-ordered integrals, simply attaches to the system “sensors” (two of them for two-photon correlations, N sensors in general) and computes correlations directly from their usual quantum averages. Technically, this requires to “plug” to the Hamiltonian of the system (in our case, Eq. (2.1)), the sensors, themselves most simply described as two-level systems ς_i whose frequencies ω_i define which frequencies are being “measured”. The name “sensor” was chosen as opposed to “detector” since correlations are obtained in the limit $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ of their vanishing coupling to the system, thereby not affecting its dynamics. This restricts their use to correlations as opposed to signal. Alternatively, one can also use the “cascading systems” [23,24], which was shown in Ref. [25] to be equivalent to the sensor method and to conveniently substitute it in cases where the signal is needed, e.g., to perform frequency-resolved Monte Carlo simulations. For resonance fluorescence, the augmented Hamiltonian thus reads:

$$H_{\sigma;\varsigma} \equiv H_\sigma + \Delta_1 \varsigma_1^\dagger \varsigma_1 + \Delta_2 \varsigma_2^\dagger \varsigma_2 + \epsilon \sum_{i=1,2} (\sigma^\dagger \varsigma_i + \varsigma_i^\dagger \sigma). \quad (2.2)$$

In the rotating frame of the laser, the frequencies $\Delta_i \equiv \omega_i - \omega_L$ are simply ω_i since $\omega_L = 0$. As a quantum-optical problem, one should include dissipation, which can be provided by a master equation in the Lindblad form, so that the dynamics for the full density matrix ρ —of the system itself as well as its sensors—is governed by the equation

$$\partial_t \rho = -i[H_\sigma, \rho] + \frac{\gamma_\sigma}{2} \mathcal{L}_\sigma \rho + \sum_{j=1,2} \frac{\gamma_j}{2} \mathcal{L}_{\varsigma_j} \rho, \quad (2.3)$$

where the Lindblad terms are of the form $\mathcal{L}_c \rho \equiv 2c\rho c^\dagger - c^\dagger c\rho - \rho c^\dagger c$ for any operator c . Importantly, in addition to the decay rate γ_σ of the two-level system, we also bring the decay rate γ_i of the i th sensor, that describes its frequency bandwidth. For two-photon observables (and higher N), such a parameter is mandatory for a physical description of the system, unlike one-photon observables like the power spectrum, which can be well described for a vanishing linewidth of their detector (recovering the Wiener-Khinchin result). In the following we shall assume the same frequency window for both sensors, i.e., $\gamma_{1,2} = \Gamma$, which we shall refer to as the “filter width” as this also corresponds to placing an interference filter before an ideal detector. The sensor method allows us to obtain the luminescence spectrum $S_\Gamma(\omega) = \frac{\Gamma}{2\pi\epsilon^2} \langle \varsigma^\dagger \varsigma \rangle(\omega)$ (no index needed since a single sensor is enough) as the population of the sensor ς placed at the frequency ω , which is a mere parameter in Eq. (2.2) as opposed to a physical observable and thus an operator, which would complicate very much the treatment. In particular, note that we need not invoke any quantum-regression theorem, Fourier transform, etc. For resonance fluorescence,

Figure 2. The two-photon physics of resonance fluorescence. **Top row:** photoluminescence spectra for (a) the Mollow triplet at resonance, (b) the detuned Mollow triplet and (c) the detuned Heitler triplet. The coherent (scattered) light is shown in yellow. **Second row:** two-photon correlation spectra $g_{\Gamma}^{(2)}(\omega_1, \omega_2)$ for the corresponding spectra, with bunching in red, no-correlation in white and antibunching or no-coincidence emission in blue. Two sets of features dominate the landscape: straight lines of bunching (red) and circles of antibunching (blue). Lines result from multiphoton transitions that involve virtual photons—“leapfrog processes”—while circles result from self-homodyning destructive interferences. **Three bottom rows:** covariance \mathcal{I}_0 (third row), anomalous two-photon moments \mathcal{I}_1 (fourth) and squeezing \mathcal{I}_2 (bottom) which sum together with 1 to the two-photon spectrum. Shaded regions refer to negative quantities. Parameters: $\gamma_{\sigma} = 1$ (setting the unit) and $\Gamma = 2$ everywhere, while $(\Delta_{\sigma}, \Omega_{\sigma}) =$ (a) (0, 40.05), (b) (60, 26.53) and (c) (80, 2).

the spectral shape has a simple, characteristic structure:

$$S_{\Gamma}(\omega) = |\langle \sigma \rangle|^2 \mathcal{L}_{\Gamma}(\omega) + (\langle \sigma^{\dagger} \sigma \rangle - |\langle \sigma \rangle|^2) \mathcal{M}_{\Gamma}(\omega) \quad (2.4)$$

where

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \frac{2\Omega_{\sigma}(2\Delta_{\sigma} + i\gamma_{\sigma})}{\gamma_{\sigma}^2 + 4\Delta_{\sigma}^2 + 8\Omega_{\sigma}^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \sigma^{\dagger} \sigma \rangle = \frac{4\Omega_{\sigma}^2}{\gamma_{\sigma}^2 + 4\Delta_{\sigma}^2 + 8\Omega_{\sigma}^2} \quad (2.5)$$

are the coherently-scattered field $\langle \sigma \rangle$ (with intensity the modulus square of this) and the total population $\langle \sigma^{\dagger} \sigma \rangle$, including the coherent part, so the incoherent part alone is $\langle \sigma^{\dagger} \sigma \rangle - |\langle \sigma \rangle|^2 = 32\Omega_{\sigma}^2/(\gamma_{\sigma}^2 + 4\Delta_{\sigma}^2 + 8\Omega_{\sigma}^2)^2$ (this happens to be $2\langle \sigma^{\dagger} \sigma \rangle^2$). These are not Γ dependent. They weight, respectively, a central Lorentzian peak $\mathcal{L}_{\Gamma}(\omega) \equiv \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\Gamma/2}{(\Gamma/2)^2 + \omega^2}$ and a symmetric triplet (both normalized), whose expression is a bit more involved:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_{\Gamma}(\omega) \equiv & \\ & \frac{2(\gamma_{12}^2 + 4\omega^2)(\gamma_{11}^2\gamma_{12} + 4\gamma_{12}\Delta_{\sigma}^2 + 4\gamma_{10}\omega^2) + 8\Omega_{\sigma}^2(\gamma_{11}\gamma_{12}\gamma_{35} + 4\gamma_{12}\Delta_{\sigma}^2 - 4\gamma_{1\bar{2}}\omega^2) + 128\Omega_{\sigma}^4\gamma_{11}}{\pi(\gamma_{12}^2 + 4\omega^2)[(\gamma_{11}^2 + 4\Delta_{\sigma}^2)^2 + 8(\gamma_{11}^2 - 4\Delta_{\sigma}^2)\omega^2 + 16\omega^4] +} \\ & + 32\Omega_{\sigma}^2[\gamma_{11}\gamma_{12}(\gamma_{11}^2 + 4\Delta_{\sigma}^2) + 4(\gamma_{01}\gamma_{11} + 4\Delta_{\sigma}^2)\omega^2 - 16\omega^4] + 256\Omega_{\sigma}^4(\gamma_{11}^2 + 4\omega^2) \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

where we use the notation $\gamma_{ij} \equiv i\Gamma + j\gamma_{\sigma}$ for any integer i, j , with also $\bar{j} = -j$ so, e.g., $\gamma_{35} = 3\Gamma + 5\gamma_{\sigma}$. The expression is not particularly enlightening but it is completely general, including the Mollow triplet and Heitler regime, at and out-of resonance, also with the effect of detection Γ . An even more complete (with incoherent pumping and dephasing) version of this expression for the “physical spectrum” of resonance fluorescence is available as a self-standing applet [26]. At any rate, its shape is simple: it is a triplet which maintains a perfect symmetry around the laser frequency set here at $\omega_L = 0$, whose interpretation in the various regimes of driving is given in Figs. 1(b) and (c). In both cases, Bohr’s insight provides a discerning picture of the otherwise mysterious spectral features of resonance fluorescence. At high-driving, the so-called “dressed atom” picture considers such quantum jumps between the dressed states $|\pm\rangle \equiv c_{\pm}|g\rangle \pm c_{\mp}|e\rangle$ of a two-level system $|g\rangle$ and $|e\rangle$ dressed by photons from a driving laser, with $c_{\pm} \equiv (1 + \xi^{\mp 2})^{-1/2}$ and $\xi \equiv \Omega_{\sigma}/[\sqrt{\Omega_{\sigma}^2 + (\Delta_{\sigma}/2)^2} + (\Delta_{\sigma}/2)]$. The central peak, at frequency ω_0 , is twice as bright than the side peaks ω_{\pm} due to two degenerate transitions $|+\rangle \rightarrow |+\rangle$ and $|-\rangle \rightarrow |-\rangle$. At low driving, now looking at the system in its bare states, a detuned laser does not make it to the excited state and so is restrained chiefly to Rayleigh (energy-conserving) scattering. However, involving two laser photons, one can match the energy ω_{σ} of the emitter with the excess energy $\omega_v \equiv 2\omega_L - \omega_{\sigma}$ (either smaller or larger than ω_{σ} depending on detuning), forming an exactly symmetric peak. This perceptive physics is well-known since the 80s [27–29]. Its understanding has little evolved since then [30].

Since the photoluminescence spectrum is a single-photon observable, one could consider a vanishing detector bandwidth $\Gamma \rightarrow 0$ (replacing γ_{ij} by $j\gamma_{\sigma}$), in which case one sees a tightening of the lines, in particular, the coherent Lorentzian $\lim_{\Gamma \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{L}_{\Gamma}(\omega)$ becomes a Dirac $\delta(\omega)$ function that reflects the vanishing linewidth of the laser treated as a c number (Ω_{σ}) in Eq. (2.1). The effect of detection is thus a mere (and expected) broadening of the lines, which does not qualitatively alter the spectral shape. The case of Heitler resonance ($\Omega_{\sigma} \ll \gamma_{\sigma}$ and $\Delta_{\sigma} = 0$) has attracted deserved but unwary attention. A short discussion will allow us to motivate the significance of detection, to which the sensor formalism gives utmost importance. The spectrum (2.6) reduces in this case to:

$$S_{\Gamma}(\omega) = \frac{4\Omega_{\sigma}^2}{\gamma_{\sigma}^2} \left[\left(1 - \frac{16\Omega_{\sigma}^2}{\gamma_{\sigma}^2}\right) \mathcal{L}_{\Gamma}(\omega) + \frac{8\Omega_{\sigma}^2}{\gamma_{\sigma}^2} \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{\gamma_{12}\gamma_{11}^2 + 4\Gamma\omega^2}{(\gamma_{11}^2 + 4\omega^2)^2} \right] \quad (2.7)$$

and, again, the $\Gamma \rightarrow 0$ appears to be a straightforward and good-enough approximation of the main features

$$S_0(\omega) = \frac{4\Omega_{\sigma}^2}{\gamma_{\sigma}^2} \left[\left(1 - \frac{16\Omega_{\sigma}^2}{\gamma_{\sigma}^2}\right) \delta(\omega) + \frac{8\Omega_{\sigma}^2}{\gamma_{\sigma}^2} \pi \gamma_{\sigma} \mathcal{L}_{\gamma_{\sigma}}^2(\omega) \right] \quad (2.8)$$

in fact making them particularly transparent, namely, as long as $\Gamma \leq \gamma_\sigma$ (sub-natural linewidth resolution), given that $\Omega_\sigma^2 \ll \gamma_\sigma^2$, the spectrum is essentially a very narrow central line sitting on a weak and broad (γ_σ) spectrum. This scenario can be seen for the central peak in panel (b) of Fig. 2. The fluorescent spectrum is, to leading order, the *square* of a Lorentzian, exposing its two-photon origin. This expression corrects the erroneous Eq. (3) in Ref. [35]. The impact of the detector in Eq. (2.8) is merely to contribute a quite innocuous broadening: one can take better and better detectors and converge to the ideal limit (2.8) which is essentially $\frac{4\Omega_\sigma^2}{\gamma_\sigma^2} \delta(\omega)$, so it would appear that we are merely discussing technical issues. That is so, at the one-photon level.

Two-photon observables, however, behave differently, at least, if taken in their entirety. The complete quantity should retain both the frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 as well as the times of detection t_1 and t_2 of both photons, or, in a steady state, the time difference $\tau \equiv t_2 - t_1$. We will introduce it in the next Section, but for now, to compare with the results found in the literature, we assume both frequencies to be that of the emitter $\omega_1 = \omega_2 = \omega_\sigma$, itself at resonance with the laser frequency ω_L , in which case the sensor formalism provides us with $g_\Gamma^{(2)}(\tau) = \langle \varsigma_1^\dagger(0) \varsigma_2^\dagger(\tau) \varsigma_1(0) \rangle / [\langle \varsigma_1^\dagger \varsigma_1 \rangle \langle \varsigma_2^\dagger \varsigma_2 \rangle]$ which evaluates to

$$g_\Gamma^{(2)}(\tau) = \left(e^{-(\Gamma + \gamma_\sigma)\tau/2} + \frac{\Gamma \gamma_\sigma}{\Gamma^2 - \gamma_\sigma^2} e^{-\Gamma\tau/2} - \frac{\Gamma^2}{\Gamma^2 - \gamma_\sigma^2} e^{-\gamma_\sigma\tau/2} \right)^2, \quad (2.9)$$

(the limit $\Gamma \rightarrow \gamma_\sigma$ gives $g_{\gamma_\sigma}^{(2)}(\tau) = [1 + (\gamma_\sigma\tau)/2] e^{-\gamma_\sigma\tau/2} - e^{-\gamma_\sigma\tau}$). The most natural way to neglect frequencies is to detect them all, which corresponds to taking the limit $\Gamma \rightarrow \infty$, in which case one recovers the result from the literature [42]:

$$g_\infty^{(2)}(\tau) = (1 - e^{-\gamma_\sigma\tau/2})^2. \quad (2.10)$$

This describes an excellent single-photon source (in particular with a flattening $\approx (\gamma_\sigma\tau/2)^2$ at small delays τ around $g^{(2)}(0) = 0$, characteristic of superior single-photon emission [31]). That is to say, one apparently has a bright very narrow—Eq. (2.8)—and antibunched—Eq. (2.10)—source. This is thanks to various ingredients contributing their respective benefits: the laser brings the narrow linewidth while the two-level system brings the single-photon emission. But in this listing of great properties, which have been experimentally demonstrated [32,33], one is using different and in fact incompatible configurations, namely, $\Gamma \rightarrow 0$ for the spectrum and $\Gamma \rightarrow \infty$ for the antibunching. In the laboratory, separate characterizations, overlooking the impact of Γ , have been performed of the system, thereby omitting a crucial adversative conjunction in describing an “ultra-coherent or single photon source” and “subnatural linewidth or single photons”. This oversight shows that Γ is not a mere technical concern but a central consideration. If working directly with Eqs. (2.7) and (2.9) instead of the textbook limits, then the intrinsic limitations imposed by detection would be obvious. The difficulty is that one needs a large enough bandwidth Γ so as to have sufficient integration time to resolve $g^{(2)}(\tau)$ while also having a small enough bandwidth to have a good frequency resolution and not suffer too much broadening. When using the wrong limit for each observable, one indeed gets the worst result possible, namely, $S_\infty(\omega)$ vanishes as the spectrum becomes constant over $(-\infty, +\infty)$ since photons are emitted at all possible energies, while $g_0^{(2)}(\tau) = 1$ and all correlations are lost. These are in fact those of an ideal laser; a physical laser has a linewidth and filtering below that linewidth would go to the thermal limit $g_0^{(2)}(\tau) = 2!$ [34], at any rate, the single-photon correlations are completely lost. Presented in these terms, it would seem that the time–frequency incompatibility occurs at the Fourier level and is thus unavoidable. But this could be easily circumvented merely by replacing the source with one that is more spectrally narrow, i.e., by reducing γ_σ , keeping the same antibunching with a broader-than-natural linewidth of the substitute emitter, but still narrower than the original one: in this way, one can realize arbitrarily narrow and antibunched source, showing that there is no fundamental limitation, only a technical one of finding the suitable emitter. In fact, even the sub-natural linewidth can be realized *simultaneously* with antibunching, provided a small, but crucial, variation of the experiments [35]. One first need to understand the nature of antibunching in this system, which, as we said, comes from the

two-level system. Or does it? Because driving is weak in this regime, the saturation of the two-level system is not actually needed, in contrast to incoherent excitation where truncation of the number of excitations is crucial (maintaining the average population below $1/2$). Here, a weak nonlinearity would work as well since the antibunching arises in this case from a two-photon approximation of squeezing antibunching [36] (this is an approximation because there is also three and higher-order antibunching which a squeezed state cannot provide). Squeezing and antibunching have a long shared history of joint appearances, initially with little appreciation of their interconnectedness [17,37,38]. This is in this way that they have been independently theorized [39,40], sought [41,42] and ultimately discovered [43,44] in resonance fluorescence. In such a system, they turn out to be two faces of the same coin, namely, of wave interferences [45]. Interferences are at the heart of both optics and quantum mechanics, so their importance in quantum optics can only be understood as momentous [46,47]. While in classical optics, the simplest waves are described by two parameters—their amplitude and phase—quantum fields come with an infinite number of amplitudes for non-Gaussian states of light, as each multiphoton component $|n\rangle$ of the field $|\psi\rangle = \sum_n c_n |n\rangle$ comes with its own independent coefficient c_n . One can produce rich multiphoton correlated outputs from admixing (or interfering) even the simplest and most popular Gaussian states [48], namely, the coherent state $|\alpha\rangle = \mathcal{D}(\alpha)|0\rangle$, defined in terms of the displacement operator $\mathcal{D}(\alpha) \equiv \exp(\alpha a^\dagger - \alpha^* a)$ where $\alpha = |\alpha|e^{i\phi}$ and a the harmonic oscillator annihilation operator, so that $(\mathcal{D})^\dagger a \mathcal{D} = a + \alpha$, and the single-mode (quadrature) squeezed state, defined in term of the squeezing operator [49,50] $S_1 \equiv \exp[\frac{1}{2}(\xi^* a^2 - \xi a^{\dagger 2})]$. The idea is as simple as for classical optics interferences: by fine-tuning their respective coefficients, one can realize destructive or constructive interferences for a given component $|n\rangle$ and thus suppress or maximize it in the output. At the Gaussian level, this comes with strong constraints since few parameters define all the multiphoton weights, but because such states are easily produced, they have elicited most of the interest. The idea of admixing squeezing with a coherent state appeared very early, precisely with the aim to produce antibunching [51] (under the name of “anticorrelation effect”), and in fact even before the more straightforward idea of a two-level system being restored into its ground state [52]. It was then believed that such squeezed anticorrelations might exist in the transient dynamics only. While antibunching from the two-level system was quickly observed [43], the one based on squeezing took more time (and with pulsed excitation) with the signal and pump of a degenerate parametric amplifier, producing both bunching and antibunching by varying the relative phase [53]. The effect was more clearly understood in terms of two-photon interferences by Ou *et al.* who also realized it in the stationary regime [54]. Now that we understand better the origin of antibunching in resonance fluorescence [55] (as squeezing antibunching), we can return to our hope of realizing it simultaneously with a subnatural linewidth. The loss of antibunching [56] in resonance fluorescence is due to the interference between the incoherent and coherent components being disrupted by the detection, which filters out the spectrally broad incoherent (squeezed) fraction more than it does the coherent (narrow) one. One could thus restore antibunching by correcting for this imbalance, which is an excess of coherent state, therefore, destructive interferences with an external laser can achieve that, as was indeed shown theoretically in Ref. [35]. Such techniques that go by the name of “homodyning” have been demonstrated experimentally to extract the quantum part of a signal [57]. Theoretically, this simply consists in adding a complex field α to the homodyned operator, so σ in our case, i.e., to substitute $\sigma \rightarrow \alpha + \sigma$ for a tunable $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ in the Hamiltonian H_σ . We will go into the details of this mechanism in Section 4 where we will generalize it to all frequencies of the system, while our current discussion is merely its particular case for photons with the same frequency. For now, it will be enough to note that evidences of such interferences and their effect on the correlations were reported in independent and complementary works that tamper with either the incoherent fraction (and thus losing antibunching) [55,58] or on the opposite with the coherent fraction (producing excess bunching instead) [59]. Restoring antibunching remains to be demonstrated experimentally. At the theoretical level, our discussion so far should have established that the detection, which

manifests itself through the parameter Γ , is at the center of quantum-optical characterizations and should not be treated lightheartedly. A deeper concept is concealed in Eq. (2.9), namely, that what is being measured is truly the correlations of photons with frequency $\omega_L = 0$, i.e., one is making a *complete* characterization of both the time *and* frequency of the photons, which is why Γ is mandatory. What the textbook limit $\Gamma \rightarrow \infty$ really does is to neglect the frequency information. This is not entirely apparent from Eq. (2.9) because it seems that no other frequency than the one at which the system emits would make sense. This is not the case. Such a complete description for more general multiphoton observables is discussed in the next Section, which embarks us on another departure with the bulk of the literature, this time not for a computational technique only, but at the conceptual level of what it means to detect multiphotons.

3. Frequency-resolved photon correlations

When considering the emission from a quantum emitter, and performing, say, two-photon correlations from its output, there is an irresistible temptation to correlate photons that are “visible” in the emission spectrum, i.e., that originate from spectral peaks. If the emission further comes in the form of several peaks, that invites for cross-correlating them. This is due to the persistence of the classical picture even to the quantum opticians, despite now many decades of quantum theory telling us that quantum states at the multi-particle level are not conditioned by their attributes at the one-particle level [60]. This makes it conceivable that multi-photon correlations can be more pronounced or interesting in spectral regions where the intensity (or population, i.e., a one-photon observable of the type $\langle a^\dagger a \rangle$) is itself small or even negligible. One must, at the quantum level, separate in principle quantity and quality. It is in fact, beyond conceivable, compulsory to elevate one’s understanding of multiphoton emission to such situations where the system does not emit at the one-photon level, but does at the two-photon one, and vice-versa. There can also be joint intense emission of the two type, or jointly suppressed. All combinations are possible. They are therefore conceptually disconnected. To see this, one needs a quantity to visualize two-photon physics, which we now introduce. Such a quantity should have no such prejudice for the spectral peaks, and treat every pair of photons the same. It should be represented on a 2D plot as it requires two axes, one for each photon. It should also extend or generalize already existing quantities as it is unlikely that the essence of two-photon physics has been missed entirely, although it might well have been left incomplete. Such a two-photon quantity we call the *two-photon spectrum* [61,62] or two-photon correlation spectrum, which we define in terms of the intensity or population operator $\hat{n}(\omega, t)$ that quantifies the amount of quantum radiation at frequency ω at time t [15], leading to:

$$g_{\Gamma}^{(2)}(\omega_1, \omega_2, t_1, t_2) = \frac{\langle \hat{n}(\omega_1, t_1) \hat{n}(\omega_2, t_2) \rangle}{\langle \hat{n}(\omega_1, t_1) \rangle \langle \hat{n}(\omega_2, t_2) \rangle}. \quad (3.1)$$

This is a clear generalization of Glauber’s two-photon correlation function, but retaining the frequency information along with the temporal one. For this reason, the detector’s bandwidth Γ is mandatory. This quantity has been considered by various Authors [63–65] but it has presented considerable difficulties and only partial results could be derived, sometimes with inconsistencies. From the sensor formalism, however, it is easily and exactly obtained as

$$g_{\Gamma}^{(2)}(\omega_1, \omega_2, t_1, t_2) = \frac{\langle (s_1^\dagger(t_1)(s_2^\dagger(s_2)(t_2)s_1(t_1))) \rangle}{\langle (s_1^\dagger(s_1)(t_1)) \rangle \langle (s_2^\dagger(s_2)(t_2)) \rangle}. \quad (3.2)$$

While one can consider both time and frequency (see, e.g., Refs. [66,67]), it will be enough for the present text to consider coincidences of a stationary state, i.e., the case $t_1 = t_2 \rightarrow \infty$. This will not diminish the main insight that in so doing, we are making a joint characterization in time (albeit coincidences only) and frequencies. We now embrace the full picture and compute numerically two-frequency coincidences (3.2) through standard quantum averages of the sensor method. Since frequencies are mere parameters, this allows a convenient and exact computation of what was previously obtained at the cost of great efforts and several oversimplifying approximations [68,

69]. The results are shown in Fig. 2's panels (d–f) [2nd row], below the corresponding spectral shapes, reproducing three notable cases from the pioneering work [62]. Unlike the top row, where $S_T(\omega)$ could be obtained in the limit $\Gamma \rightarrow 0$, these two-photon spectra would become “trivial” in this limit, with $g_0^{(2)}(\omega_1, \omega_2) = 1$, i.e., washing out all traces of correlations as the detectors integrate over infinite times. The other limit is more interesting but brings nothing new as it recovers Eq. (2.10), and so, at $\tau = 0$, is identically zero. What is of interest, clearly, is the intermediate case where a landscape of correlations is revealed. It will be enough to limit ourselves with a description of the qualitative features, although we repeat that the results are numerically exact, so one could study cross sections in more quantitative details. In our qualitative description, red colors correspond to bunching, i.e., to photons with the respective frequencies arriving together, with antidiagonals of bunching in cases (a) and (b) that correspond to the two-photon Mollow triplet. These lines indeed generalize Bohr's quantization condition for transitions between two energies $E_i - E_j = \omega$, to a two-photon jump

$$E_k - E_l = \omega_1 + \omega_2 \quad (3.3)$$

where the energies E_k and E_l are non-contiguous in the energy ladder and so the system effectively “jumps over” a real state, for which reason this has been termed a *leapfrog process* [61, 62]. This is the direct quantum-optical counterpart of Göpert Mayer's *Doppelemission* with a few but important variations. In her case, there was nothing to jump over, and the multiphoton emission was thus in a different frequency range, indeed, in its manifestation from nebulae emission, this converts UV $2S \rightarrow 1S$ Lyman photons into the visual continuum siding with the visible Balmer series $X \rightarrow 2S$. Higher-order processes fall into still more remote spectral windows, while our leapfrog processes, even from three or higher-number of photons, are all over the place along with the single photons that one sees in the spectral shape. The second variation is our reliance on the quantum-optical quantity $g_T^{(2)}(\omega_1, \omega_2)$ (this would be $g^{(n)}$ for higher photon numbers), which allows to “reveal” this hitherto unsuspected structure, whose existence is, again, not conditioned to the amount of signal, and can be captured by using an adequate two-photon observable, which, as Glauber clarified for quantum light, is the intensity-intensity correlator [60]. As a result, one should look for such multiphoton emission *everywhere*, not only when it is betrayed, for one reason or another, at the one-photon level. In most cases, it remains invisible (at the one photon level). The appropriate photon correlations allow us to extract them from a background of unrelated or more intense emission. Another variation is that, two-photon light being more complex than single-photon one, it comes with more characteristics, that we can capture with colors as opposed to a magnitude. We use white for uncorrelated emission where the two photons are emitted independently the one from the other. Interestingly, one can see in Fig. 2 that such uncorrelated photons form a grid of horizontal and vertical lines defined by the (one photon) spectral peaks. This means that photons from the spectrum contribute not only the bulk, indeed, of the emission, but more significantly, the classical signal which is independent from the rest of the emission. This is another call for quantum opticians to seek their photons away from the peaks: quantum photons are emitted where one does not seem them. This is because photons from the spectral peaks are “real” photons that arise from the Bohrian jump from one real (here, dressed) state to another, while leapfrog photons are virtual, in the sense that they involve a virtual intermediate state with energy E_l^* which could be any value in between, and thus resulting in a correlated signal for the entire line satisfying Eq. (3.3). Virtual does not mean “non-existing” and would one still complain of no emission outside from the peaks, we would retort again that this is a one-photon concern. The no-emission at the two-photon level is unrelated to no-emission at the one-photon one. No two-photon emission is in fact what we encode with the blue color in the two-photon spectrum. And one can see in Fig. 2(d) how the strongest no two-photon emission occurs at $(\varpi_1, \varpi_2) = (-1, -1)$ or $(+1, +1)$, i.e., at the spectral side peaks, where one-photon emission is indeed strong. Such a scenario is well known, as it corresponds to single-photon emission. In contrast, at $(\varpi_1, \varpi_2) = \frac{1}{2}(-1, -1)$ or $\frac{1}{2}(+1, +1)$, one has the opposite situation of strong two-photon emission but small one-photon emission (in fact the smallest emission in the

range $|\varpi| \lesssim 1.25$), which corresponds to the equally fundamental case of two-photon leapfrog emission, which may be even more important than single-photon emission, although, because it is innocuous at the one-photon level, it failed to attract much attention so far. One must highlight in this regard the exceptional contributions from the beautiful and still unique experiments of the Muller group [70–73], who has observed these features in spectacular agreement with the theory. Finally, a manifestation of the independent yet tangible existence of the two-photon physics can be based on arguments of theoretical aesthetics: the robust spectral (one-photon) symmetry, which appears to be lifted at the two-photon level since the two peaks behave differently in the two-photon spectrum, is instead “rotated”: the symmetry is with respect to the two-photon diagonal, so independent from the one-photon structure, but also present when looked at properly. This needed change of perspective, we believe, is an evidence of the independent two-photon picture. If such arguments fail to move one’s sensibility, and although we are focused on the fundamental aspects in this text, we should then mention that there are obvious and immediate technological prospects of these results that turn these correlated virtual photons into quantum emission of a new type. For instance, placing a cavity at the N -photon leapfrog degenerate frequency (halfway between the peaks for two photons) would Purcell-enhance their emission and open a bright channel of pure N -photon emission [74]. This is clearly another evidence of the “existence” of such processes, that can power devices of a new type. There are other ways to similarly exploit this hidden physics, but we wish to return instead to its basic structure, and now focus on the perplexing blue circle cast between the central and virtual peaks, as seen in Fig. 2(f). This circle is of a different nature from the phenomenology that we have discussed so far, since this is a curve as opposed to straight lines, and suppressing photons instead of having them come together as joint emission. We now explain here for the first time the underlying mechanism for this circle.

4. Admixing two-mode squeezed and coherent states

Two-photon physics is primarily described by Fock states $|2\rangle$ in a given mode, or by non-degenerate pairs $|1_1 1_2\rangle$ in two modes. Next comes the so-called *squeezed states*, which was popularized by Walls [75] for their ability to squeeze through the uncertainty principle [76], but were initially (and possibly, more appropriately) called “two-photon coherent states” by Yuen [77]. Because two-photon spectra correlate two frequencies (providing two continuously varying modes), two-mode squeezing can be expected to have some relevance in presence of coherence, as is the case for resonance fluorescence. Two-mode squeezing considers two bosonic modes with annihilation operators a_1 and a_2 , and a so-called “squeezing matrix” ζ_{ij} (complex-valued symmetric). The two-mode squeezing operator [78]

$$\mathcal{S}_2^{(ij)} = \exp[\zeta_{ij} a_i a_j - \zeta_{ij}^* a_i^\dagger a_j^\dagger], \quad (4.1)$$

can be seen as a generalization of the already introduced single-mode squeezing operator

$$\mathcal{S}_1^{(i)} = \exp\left[\frac{1}{2}(\xi_i^* a_i^2 - \xi_i a_i^\dagger{}^2)\right], \quad (4.2)$$

where the squeezing parameters are conveniently defined as $\xi_i = r_i e^{i\theta_i}$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $\zeta_{ij} = t_{ij} e^{i\vartheta_{ij}}$ a matrix with zero diagonal elements, namely $\zeta_{12} = t_{12} e^{i\vartheta_{12}}$ with $\zeta_{jj} = 0$ for $j = 1, 2$. One can squeeze the two modes independently, with the product of the single-mode squeezing operators $\mathcal{S}_1^{(1)}(\xi_1) \mathcal{S}_1^{(2)}(\xi_2) = \mathcal{S}_1^{(2)}(\xi_2) \mathcal{S}_1^{(1)}(\xi_1)$ (the operators commute), or squeeze them jointly with the two-mode squeezing operator $\mathcal{S}_2^{(12)}(\zeta_{12})$, transforming annihilation operators as [78]:

$$(\mathcal{S}_2^{(12)})^\dagger a_i \mathcal{S}_2^{(12)} = \sum_{k=1,2} (\mathcal{M}_{ik} a_k - \mathcal{N}_{ik} a_k^\dagger), \quad (4.3)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq 2$. The mixing matrix \mathcal{M} is positive while the second mixing matrix \mathcal{N} can be complex-valued. For single-mode squeezing, they are diagonal with values $\mathcal{M}_{ii} = \cosh(r_i)$ and $\mathcal{N}_{ii} = e^{i\theta_i} \sinh(r_i)$, respectively. On the other hand, for two-mode squeezing, the non-vanishing elements are $\mathcal{M}_{11} = \mathcal{M}_{22} = \cosh(t_{12})$ and $\mathcal{N}_{12} = \mathcal{N}_{21} = e^{i\vartheta_{12}} \sinh(t_{12})$. This leads to

the transformation rules for the one- and two-mode operators:

$$(\mathcal{S}_1^{(i)})^\dagger a_i \mathcal{S}_1^{(i)} = \mu_i a_i - \nu_i a_i^\dagger \quad \text{and} \quad (\mathcal{S}_2^{(12)})^\dagger a_i \mathcal{S}_2^{(12)} = \mathcal{M}_{11} a_i - \mathcal{N}_{12} a_i^\dagger, \quad (4.4)$$

where $\mu_i = \cosh(r_i)$, $\nu_i = e^{i\theta_i} \sinh(r_i)$, $\mathcal{M}_{11} = \cosh(t_{12})$, $\mathcal{N}_{12} = e^{i\vartheta_{12}} \sinh(t_{12})$ and $\bar{i} \equiv 3 - i$ exchanges 1 and 2. Alternatively, one could use the general form of $\mathcal{S}_2^{(12)}$, with structurally identical results. The combination of these squeezing leads to a generic two-mode squeezed state:

$$|\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta_{12}\rangle \equiv \mathcal{S}_1^{(1)} \mathcal{S}_1^{(2)} \mathcal{S}_2^{(12)} |00\rangle. \quad (4.5)$$

For this state, it is straightforward to compute any correlator $\langle a_1^\dagger{}^m a_1^n a_2^\dagger{}^p a_2^q \rangle$ for integers m, n, p, q from Eqs. (4.3). For instance, we find for the population of mode $i = 1, 2$:

$$\langle a_i^\dagger a_i \rangle = \cosh^2 r_i \sinh^2 t + \sinh^2 r_i \cosh^2 t. \quad (4.6)$$

One could carry-on like this and compute other correlators but since we shall be concerned in the following with leading-order processes, we can rescale the squeezing parameters as $r_i \rightarrow \epsilon^2 r_i$ and $t \rightarrow \epsilon^2 t$ for an ϵ that will be taken close to zero. In this limit, thanks to normalization, we can give a more comprehensive list of the correlators, including the second-order correlation functions $g_i^{(2)} \equiv \langle a_i^\dagger{}^2 a_i^2 \rangle / \langle a_i^\dagger a_i \rangle^2$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $g_{12}^{(2)} \equiv \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger a_2 a_1 \rangle / \langle a_1^\dagger a_1 \rangle \langle a_2^\dagger a_2 \rangle$:

$$\langle a_i^\dagger a_i \rangle \approx (r_i^2 + t_{12}^2) \epsilon^4, \quad \langle a_1 a_2 \rangle \approx -\epsilon^2 \zeta_{12}, \quad \langle a_i^2 \rangle \approx -\epsilon^2 \xi_i, \quad (4.7a)$$

$$g_i^{(2)} \approx \frac{r_i^4}{(r_i^2 + t_{12}^2)(r_2^2 + t_{12}^2) \epsilon^4}, \quad g_{12}^{(2)} \approx \frac{t_{12}^4}{(r_1^2 + t_{12}^2)(r_2^2 + t_{12}^2) \epsilon^4}. \quad (4.7b)$$

Since ϵ is very small, one can see that all the two-particle fluctuations are bunched. We can, however, produce antibunching by interfering squeezing with a coherent state, as we already discussed for the Heitler regime at resonance. Here, we will look more closely at the general case of interferences that involve two-mode squeezing, and show that this captures much of the two-photon physics of resonance fluorescence. This extends to two modes the idea already scrutinized for one mode [16,35], that admixture of coherence with squeezing results in rich and qualitatively different correlations than those available in the squeezed or coherent states alone. This should similarly allow to generalize the specific technique of tuning photon statistics with coherent fields [48] to multimode correlations, especially as multimode coherent states are not correlated, so they can be tuned independently for each squeezed modes. From the weak driving that defines resonance fluorescence, it is enough to deal with coherent-squeezed states in the limit of small squeezing. Since the coherent contribution of the quantum states is taken of the same order than squeezing, we take $\alpha_i \rightarrow \epsilon \alpha_i$, meaning, however, that coherence is stronger since it appears to first order in the admixture while squeezing is of second order. This brings us to the fundamental object of two-photon resonance fluorescence:

$$|\alpha, \xi, \zeta_{12}\rangle = \mathcal{D}_1 \mathcal{D}_2 \mathcal{S}_1^{(1)} \mathcal{S}_1^{(2)} \mathcal{S}_2^{(12)} |00\rangle, \quad (4.8)$$

where $\alpha \equiv (\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$ and $\xi \equiv (\xi_1, \xi_2)$ admixes coherence and squeezing of single modes [48] along with ζ_{12} that provides the general two-photon physics. Similarly as before, we can now compute the key two-photon correlators for this state, to leading order in ϵ :

$$\langle a_i^\dagger a_i \rangle \approx \epsilon^2 |\alpha_i|^2 + \epsilon^4 \{ t_{12}^2 + r_i^2 - 2|\alpha_i|^2 r_i \cos(2\phi_i - \theta_i) - 2|\alpha_1||\alpha_2| t_{12} \cos(\phi_1 + \phi_2 - \vartheta_{12}) \}, \quad (4.9a)$$

$$\langle a_i^2 \rangle \approx \epsilon^2 (\alpha_i^2 - \xi_i), \quad \langle a_1 a_2 \rangle \approx \epsilon^2 (\alpha_1 \alpha_2 - \zeta_{12}), \quad (4.9b)$$

$$g_i^{(2)} \approx 1 - \frac{2 r_i \cos(2\phi_i - \theta_i)}{|\alpha_i|^2} + \frac{r_i^2}{|\alpha_i|^4}, \quad (4.9c)$$

$$g_{12}^{(2)} \approx 1 - \frac{2 t \cos(\phi_1 + \phi_2 - \vartheta_{12})}{|\alpha_1||\alpha_2|} + \frac{t_{12}^2}{|\alpha_1|^2 |\alpha_2|^2}, \quad (4.9d)$$

for $1 \leq i, j \leq 2$. As compared to Eqs. (4.7), one can see that the correlators $g^{(2)}$ can now take a much wider span of possible values, in particular they can now be less than unity and even vanish exactly as well as diverge to leading order. This is the two-mode generalization of our previous single-mode admixing [48], where it was also the case that the population, Eq. (4.9a), is essentially coherent, since $\epsilon^2 \gg \epsilon^4$, but that, regardless of this preponderance of the coherent state, two-photon observables are ruled by the squeezing component. Here too, the intensity of the squeezed photons has to be much smaller than the coherent one. The reason is that in order to interfere at the two-photon level (to produce antibunching) the contributions have to be of the same order, what we have achieved thanks to the parametrization. The coherent field makes the system gain one photon, with a probability proportional to $|\alpha_i|$. To climb up from vacuum to $|2\rangle$, the system has to absorb two photons, one each time, so the chances are proportional to $|\alpha_i|^2$. On the other hand, the squeezed field carries the photons two by two. Then, the system can directly jump from $|0\rangle$ to $|2\rangle$ by absorbing two photons with a probability proportional to r_i . To ensure that both processes compete on equal footing, the ratio $|\alpha_i|^2/r_i$ has to remain finite when the limits $|\alpha_i|, r_i \rightarrow 0$ are taken. For the two-mode case, the interference yields the cancellation of the $|1, 1\rangle$ state and the argument is exactly the same just exchanging $|\alpha_i|^2 \rightarrow |\alpha_1||\alpha_2|$ and $r_i \rightarrow t_{12}$. This explains the counter-intuitive fact that a weak incoherent fraction determines the antibunching of an intense coherent radiation [25,55]. A major departure from two-mode squeezing as compared to single-mode admixing, is the degeneracy for the conditions that realize interferences producing extreme correlations, such as perfect antibunching (exact zero) or diverging superbunching. Indeed, perfect anticorrelation for a single mode is obtained when these conditions are fulfilled:

$$r_i = |\alpha_i|^2, \quad 2\phi_i - \theta_i = 0, \quad (4.10)$$

while two-mode anticorrelations are maximized when:

$$t_{12} = |\alpha_1\alpha_2|, \quad \phi_1 + \phi_2 - \vartheta_{12} = 0. \quad (4.11)$$

Just like two-photon leapfrog transitions (cf. Sec. 3) lift the strict conservation of energy for each photon to constrain their sum instead—allowing each photon in the pair to come with a continuous energy [62,67]—here, the wave-interference is realized for a sum of the phases, in contrast to the single phase for a single mode [16]. This allows, again, for a continuous range of parameters to realize the quantum interference. Such admixtures can be tracked in any dynamical two-mode quantum state, possibly mixed with a density matrix ρ . We will consider, explicitly, the case of resonance fluorescence, which is the simplest one, but of course our discussion is general, whether the coherence is provided internally (as is the case in resonance fluorescence where it is inherited from the coherent driving) or is explicitly added externally, with a supplementary (homodyning) laser, a case we shall also touch upon. It could also be developed by the system itself (e.g., when it undergoes lasing). Whatever the origin for the various contributions, one can separate them from the whole operators a_i that act on the whole state from those \tilde{a}_i that act only on the fluctuations, or incoherent part. They are linked by the relation

$$a_i = \alpha_i + \tilde{a}_i \quad (4.12)$$

where, again, a_i and \tilde{a}_i are operators while α_i is a c -number. This again generalizes our earlier case [48] and while we limit ourselves here to $i = 1, 2$, one could further extend it to any number of modes. By construction, one has $\langle \tilde{a}_i \rangle = 0$, resulting in no interferences for the intensities: $\langle a_i^\dagger a_i \rangle = |\alpha_i|^2 + \langle \tilde{a}_i^\dagger \tilde{a}_i \rangle$. In stark contrast, the cross-correlator $\langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger a_2 a_1 \rangle$ becomes $\langle (\tilde{a}_1^\dagger + \alpha_1^*)(\tilde{a}_2^\dagger + \alpha_2^*)(a_2 + \alpha_2)(a_1 + \alpha_1) \rangle$. Expanding this, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger a_2 a_1 \rangle &= \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2^\dagger \tilde{a}_2 \tilde{a}_1 \rangle + \sum_{i=1,2} (\alpha_i \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2^\dagger \tilde{a}_i \rangle + \text{cc}) + \\ &+ (\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2^\dagger \rangle + \alpha_1 \alpha_2^* \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2 \rangle + \text{cc}) + \sum_{i=1,2} |\alpha_i|^2 \langle \tilde{a}_i^\dagger \tilde{a}_i \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

where $\bar{i} \equiv 3 - i$, i.e., toggles the index in $\{1, 2\}$. This shows that, unlike intensities, the second-order correlation functions are the result of interferences, namely, of four terms:

$$g_{12}^{(2)} = 1 + \mathcal{I}_0 + \mathcal{I}_1 + \mathcal{I}_2, \quad (4.14)$$

with

$$\mathcal{I}_0 \equiv \frac{1}{n_1 n_2} \left\{ \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2^\dagger \tilde{a}_2 \tilde{a}_1 \rangle - \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_1 \rangle \langle \tilde{a}_2^\dagger \tilde{a}_2 \rangle \right\}, \quad (4.15a)$$

$$\mathcal{I}_1 \equiv \frac{2}{n_1 n_2} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \alpha_1 \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2^\dagger \tilde{a}_2 \rangle + \alpha_2 \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2^\dagger \tilde{a}_1 \rangle \right\}, \quad (4.15b)$$

$$\mathcal{I}_2 \equiv \frac{2}{n_1 n_2} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2^\dagger \rangle + \alpha_1 \alpha_2^* \langle \tilde{a}_1^\dagger \tilde{a}_2 \rangle \right\}, \quad (4.15c)$$

with $n_i \equiv \langle a_i^\dagger a_i \rangle$ so that in each case, $\mathcal{I}_i n_1 n_2$ is of order $|\alpha_1|^p |\alpha_2|^q$ with $p + q = i$. We now have recovered the general version of the phenomenon discussed in Section 2 of antibunching produced by an interference of various contributions, which are the single-mode \mathcal{I}_i , i.e., with $a_1 = a_2 = a$, in which case \mathcal{I}_0 is related to the $g^{(2)}$ of the incoherent fraction, being -1 for non-Gaussian (quantum) antibunching and $+1$ for chaotic, bunched states, while \mathcal{I}_2 is related to squeezing, being -2 in presence of squeezing. \mathcal{I}_1 is a measure of anomalous moments which is negligible in the two regimes of interest, namely

- Heitler regime, where $g^{(2)} = 0 = 1 + (\mathcal{I}_0 = 1) + (\mathcal{I}_1 = 0) + (\mathcal{I}_2 = -2)$,
- Mollow regime, where $g^{(2)} = 0 = 1 + (\mathcal{I}_0 = -1) + (\mathcal{I}_1 = 0) + (\mathcal{I}_2 = 0)$,

with, therefore, a completely different interpretation for how $g^{(2)} = 0$ is obtained. In the general case that we consider here, the numerator of \mathcal{I}_1 has the physical meaning of a covariance between the incoherent fractions, being positive when both modes are occupied or depleted together, and negative when one is largely occupied and the other depleted. As for the single-mode, the normalization is to the *total* population, not to that of the incoherent fraction alone. \mathcal{I}_2 also has some interpretation in terms of two-mode squeezing, in particular including the coherent fractions α_1 and α_2 . We shall similarly disregard the exact meaning of \mathcal{I}_1 that interpolates between the two cases by involving anomalous correlators of the population and order parameter of the type $\langle a_i \hat{n}_i \rangle$, also weighted by the coherent fraction α_i^* . We can also write these expressions not for the quantum fields only (fluctuations), but for the full-state correlators, which might be more accessible either experimentally or theoretically. To do so, we can use the backward relation:

$$\langle \tilde{a}_1^{\dagger i} \tilde{a}_2^{\dagger j} \tilde{a}_2^k \tilde{a}_1^l \rangle = \sum_{i', j', k', l'=0}^{i, j, k, l} (-1)^{i'+j'+k'+l'} \binom{i}{i'} \binom{j}{j'} \binom{k}{k'} \binom{l}{l'} (\alpha_1^*)^{i-i'} (\alpha_2^*)^{j-j'} \alpha_2^{k-k'} \alpha_1^{l-l'} \times \langle a_1^{\dagger(i-i')} a_2^{\dagger(j-j')} a_1^{k-k'} a_2^{l-l'} \rangle, \quad (4.16)$$

which applied to \mathcal{I}_i leads to:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_0 = & (\langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger a_2 a_1 \rangle - \langle a_1^\dagger a_1 \rangle \langle a_2^\dagger a_2 \rangle - 4 |\alpha_1|^2 |\alpha_2|^2 + 2 |\alpha_1|^2 \langle a_2^\dagger a_2 \rangle + \\ & 2 |\alpha_2|^2 \langle a_1^\dagger a_1 \rangle + 2 \operatorname{Re} \{ \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger \rangle + \alpha_1 \alpha_2^* \langle a_1^\dagger a_2 \rangle - \alpha_1 \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger a_2 \rangle - \alpha_2 \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger a_1 \rangle \}) / n_1 n_2, \end{aligned} \quad (4.17a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_1 = & 2 \operatorname{Re} (\alpha_1 \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger a_2 \rangle + \alpha_2 \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger a_1 \rangle - 2 \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger \rangle - 2 \alpha_1 \alpha_2^* \langle a_1^\dagger a_2 \rangle + \\ & 2 |\alpha_1|^2 |\alpha_2|^2 - |\alpha_1|^2 \langle a_2^\dagger a_2 \rangle - |\alpha_2|^2 \langle a_1^\dagger a_1 \rangle) / n_1 n_2, \end{aligned} \quad (4.17b)$$

$$\mathcal{I}_2 = 2 \operatorname{Re} (\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \langle a_1^\dagger a_2^\dagger \rangle + \alpha_1 \alpha_2^* \langle a_1^\dagger a_2 \rangle - 2 |\alpha_1|^2 |\alpha_2|^2) / n_1 n_2. \quad (4.17c)$$

One can recover from this general result the particular case (4.8) of a coherent squeezed state by checking that these quantities for $|\alpha, \xi, \zeta_{12}\rangle$ with vanishing amplitudes ($\alpha_i \rightarrow \epsilon \alpha_i$ $r_i \rightarrow \epsilon^2 r_i$

and $t_{12} \rightarrow \epsilon^2 t_{12}$, with $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$), read

$$\mathcal{I}_0 \approx \frac{t_{12}^2}{|\alpha_1|^2 |\alpha_2|^2}, \quad \mathcal{I}_2 \approx -\frac{2t_{12} \cos(\phi_1 + \phi_2 - \vartheta_{12})}{|\alpha_1| |\alpha_2|}, \quad (4.18)$$

while the anomalous \mathcal{I}_1 exactly zero for any set of parameters. This recovers Eq. (4.9d) from Eq. (4.14) and, with the conditions for the cancellation of $g_{12}^{(2)}$ in Eq. (4.11), this gives

$$\mathcal{I}_0 \approx 1, \quad \mathcal{I}_2 \approx -2, \quad (4.19)$$

i.e., the compensation between the mean field and the squeezed two-mode fluctuations that leads to $g_{12}^{(2)} = 0$ at first order in the parameters and that we also find in the single-mode antibunching [48,55]. All the previous considerations would be interesting, but formal results only, would it not be for the link that photodetection offers to the theory of frequency-resolved photon correlations, as discussed in Section 3. Namely, retaining the frequency information of the photons that one correlates, brings to the fore the decomposition Eq. (4.14) but now for the continuously varying frequencies ω_i as opposed to independent modes a_i . We now turn to such a dynamical setting.

5. Squeezed cavity

We now return to the two-photon spectrum, to reveal how the concepts of squeezed and coherent admixtures introduced in Section 4 explain the results we reported for resonance fluorescence, as shown in Fig. 2. We can best show that this is the case by bringing directly all these components externally to a cavity a and collect the re-emitted admixed light, instead of a two-level system producing them internally. This approach also invites closer inspection of such excitation schemes [79]. The sensor technique for this scenario produces the Hamiltonian:

$$H_a = \Delta_a a^\dagger a + i \frac{\Lambda_a}{2} (a^{\dagger 2} - a^2) + \Omega_a (e^{i\vartheta} a^\dagger + e^{-i\vartheta} a) + \Delta_1 \varsigma_1^\dagger \varsigma_1 + \Delta_2 \varsigma_2^\dagger \varsigma_2 + \epsilon \sum_{i=1,2} (a^\dagger \varsigma_i + \varsigma_i^\dagger a). \quad (5.1)$$

Here we have a passive, linear cavity a , driven by both a squeezed source with strength Λ_a and a laser with amplitude Ω_a , with ϑ is the phase difference between the coherent and squeezed sources. In resonance fluorescence, only the coherent state is provided externally while the weak nonlinearity, given the weak driving, produces the squeezing. In other cases, everything could be produced by the system itself (e.g., like the Mollow triplet produced under incoherent pumping when placed in a cavity that undergoes lasing [80]). While the 2LS is inherently antibunched ($g_{\sigma\sigma}^{(2)}(0) = 0$), independent of the nature and strength of the driving, a squeezed coherent cavity may modulate the photon statistics from bunched to antibunched as the parameters change. Since we are interested in showing the similarity of this system with resonance fluorescence, we first seek to find the conditions that minimize the cavity's two-photon correlator $g_a^{(2)}$. In the steady-state, the bare correlations of the squeezed cavity are

$$\langle a \rangle = -\frac{2i\Omega_a [e^{i\vartheta} (\gamma_a - 2i\Delta_a) - 2e^{-i\vartheta} \Lambda_a]}{\gamma_a^2 + 4\Delta_a^2 - 4\Lambda_a^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle a^\dagger a \rangle = \frac{2\Lambda_a^2}{\gamma_a^2 + 4\Delta_a^2 - 4\Lambda_a^2} + |\langle a \rangle|^2. \quad (5.2)$$

We do not provide the expression for the general $g_a^{(2)}$ as it is too voluminous and not immediately needed for our discussion, unlike the variance $\langle a^2 \rangle - \langle a \rangle^2 = \Lambda_a (\gamma_a - 2i\Delta_a) / [\gamma_a^2 + 4\Delta_a^2 - 4\Lambda_a^2]$ that is required for the phase matching $\theta = 2\phi$ between $\phi \equiv \arg(\langle a \rangle)$ and $\theta \equiv \arg(\langle a^2 \rangle - \langle a \rangle^2)$ needed to minimize $g_a^{(2)}$. This is satisfied for $\tan(2\vartheta) = 2\Delta_a / \gamma_a$. There is an upper-bound for the squeezing amplitude Λ_a beyond which the system is unstable and results in unphysical steady states, namely, it must be that $\Lambda_a < \sqrt{\gamma_a^2 + 4\Delta_a^2} / 2$. Reparameterizing Λ_a as $\Lambda_a = \Gamma_a \lambda / 2$ where $\Gamma_a \equiv \sqrt{\gamma_a^2 + 4\Delta_a^2}$, expresses this stability condition to $\lambda < 1$. The cavity phase and its population

in the phase-matching, i.e., optimum-antibunching configuration, are then found as

$$\langle a \rangle = \frac{2i\Omega_a\sqrt{\gamma_a - 2i\Delta_a}}{(1+\lambda)\Gamma_a^3} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle a^\dagger a \rangle = (1+\lambda)^{-2} \left[\frac{4\Omega_a^2}{\Gamma_a^2} + \frac{\lambda^2(1+\lambda)}{2(1-\lambda)} \right], \quad (5.3)$$

with now a tractable two-photon coincidences phase-matched Glauber correlator (in the $\Gamma \rightarrow \infty$ limit):

$$g^{(2)}_{a(0)} = \frac{(1-\lambda)^2}{[\Gamma_a^2\lambda^2(\lambda^2-1) - 8\Omega_a^2(1-\lambda^2)]^2} \times \\ [\Gamma_a^4\lambda^2(1+\lambda)^2(1+2\lambda^2) + 16\Omega_a^2\Gamma_a^2\lambda(\lambda^2-1)(1-2\lambda) + 64(1-\lambda)^2\Omega_a^4]. \quad (5.4)$$

Deriving Eq. (5.4) with respect to Ω_a , we find the minimum value possible for $g_a^{(2)}$ of a squeezed cavity admixed to a coherent state:

$$g_{a,\min}^{(2)} = 2 \frac{\lambda(2-\lambda)}{1+2\lambda-\lambda^2} \stackrel{\lambda \rightarrow 0}{\approx} 0 + 4\lambda, \quad (5.5)$$

which is obtained for the ‘‘optimum’’ driving $\Omega_{a,\text{optmin}}$:

$$\Omega_{a,\text{optmin}} = \frac{\Gamma_a\sqrt{\lambda/2}(1+\lambda)}{2(1-\lambda)} \stackrel{\lambda \rightarrow 0}{\approx} \frac{\Gamma_a}{2}\sqrt{\lambda/2}. \quad (5.6)$$

This produces antibunching for the whole range $0 \leq \lambda < 1$ and reaches zero as λ gets smaller (for both $A_a \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta_a \rightarrow \infty$, which is the case of interest). Applying the optimum antibunching conditions in the limiting case $\Delta_a \rightarrow \infty$ and, therefore $\lambda \rightarrow 0$, we get for the spectrum

$$S_{a,\Gamma}(\omega) \approx |\langle a \rangle|^2 \mathcal{L}_\Gamma(\omega) + (\langle a^\dagger a \rangle - |\langle a \rangle|^2) \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{\gamma_{12}(\gamma_{11}^2 + 4\Delta_a^2) + 4\Gamma\omega^2}{(\gamma_{11}^2 + 4\omega^2)^2 + 8\Delta_a^2(\gamma_{11}^2 - 4\omega^2) + 16\Delta_a^4} \quad (5.7)$$

where we also used the shortcut $\gamma_{ij} \equiv i\Gamma + j\gamma_a$ but this time for γ_a . We will now show that this matches exactly the two-level system result. The same occurs for the two-photon correlator for the squeezed cavity,

$$g_a^{(2)}(\tau) \approx 1 + e^{-\gamma_a\tau} - 2e^{-\gamma_a/2\tau} \cos(2\Delta_a\tau), \quad (5.8)$$

which is identical at resonance to the expression for the unfiltered two-level system, cf. Eq. (2.10). In the Next Section, we show that the agreement holds also in presence of detuning. We conclude this preliminary Section with the numerically exact two-photon spectrum for the squeezed cavity in the optimum phase-matching, $\theta = 2\phi$, and pumping, Eq. (5.6), conditions, which is shown in Fig. 3(a). Its excellent qualitative agreement for most of the features with resonance fluorescence involving the two-level system, is obvious (cf. Fig. 2(f)). This confirms the central importance of quantum state interferences in general and of coherent and squeezed states in particular, to account for the phenomenology of two-photon physics of detuned resonance fluorescence. This is fully established in the next Section.

6. Detuned resonance fluorescence

We can now complete our argument by returning to the two-photon spectrum of resonance fluorescence (i.e., for the two-level system σ). We will focus on detuning, since this highlights various features of interest, starting with the spectral separation of the coherent peak, which stays pinned at the center, from the incoherent emission, that splits into the symmetric doublet of side peaks, with a neat interpretation in terms of two-photon scattering as sketched in Fig. 1(c) [29]. Our goal now is to show that the one and two-photon spectra of the coherently-squeezed cavity derived in the previous Section, are, beyond their qualitative agreement with the two-level system, in fact in quantitative agreement to leading order in the driving. This will confirm that in this detuned Heitler regime, and at the two-photon level, the main role of the two-level system is to bring in a component of squeezing, and that the observed phenomenology then follows from two-mode interferences between squeezed and coherent states, with frequencies spanning

Figure 3. Three manifestations of the origin of the circles of antibunching: (a) The numerical two-photon spectrum for the squeezed cavity reproduces an almost identical structure to that of exact resonance fluorescence (cf. Fig. 2(f)). (b) the circle is removed when the coherent fraction itself is removed (by homodyning), leaving only the strong superbunching leapfrog processes. (c) The analytical expression also provides exact straight lines and a circle appearing as Eqs. (6.5–6.6) and Eq. (6.4), respectively. The mesh of thin lines are those observed in some two-photon landscapes that go beyond the physics covered in this text. Parameters: (a) $\gamma_a = 1$, $\Delta_a = 80.1$, $\lambda_a = 0.001$ and $\Gamma = 2$, optimizing antibunching. Panel (b) is the same as Fig. 2(f) but with an external homodyning field $\alpha = -\langle \sigma \rangle$.

over all possible modes of the system. The one-photon detuned Heitler spectrum $S_\Gamma(\omega)$ from Eq. (2.4), with $\Delta_\sigma \gg \Omega_\sigma$, indeed recovers the squeezed-coherent cavity spectrum (5.7) with the correspondence $\frac{\Omega_\sigma^2}{\Delta_\sigma^2} \rightarrow \frac{\Lambda_a}{2|\Delta_a|}$ (which are the populations $\langle \sigma^\dagger \sigma \rangle$ and $\langle a^\dagger a \rangle$, respectively). The same occurs with two-photon correlations, although the general expression being awkward, it is not practical to display here their mathematical identity, which we have, however, checked. We can, instead, highlight particular cases of interest, including the insightful tampering of the photon interferences by filtering out the central peak with a notch filter [59]. In this case, instead of filtering part of the spectrum and correlating it, one filters out another part and correlate what remains. Such an observable could be derived using the frequency-filtered approach described previously, but filtering out the coherent peak is more expediently achieved by homodyning it out, admixing the total luminescence with a laser of matching amplitude α but with opposite phase. If we parameterize this field as $\alpha = -\mathcal{F}\langle \sigma \rangle$ in terms of $0 \leq \mathcal{F} \leq 1$, the two-photon correlations for the homodyned field are found as:

$$g_{\mathcal{F}}^{(2)}(\tau) = 1 + \frac{1}{(1-\mathcal{F})^4} e^{-\gamma_\sigma \tau} - \frac{2}{(1-\mathcal{F})^2} e^{-(\gamma_\sigma/2)\tau} \cos(\Delta_\sigma \tau) \quad (6.1)$$

where the homodyning is varied from $\mathcal{F} = 0$ (no correction, so the full emission is taken) in which case Eq. (5.8) is recovered, to $\mathcal{F} = 1$, where the coherent peak is removed completely (so only the incoherent emission is taken), in which case one observes a simple and smooth bunching $g_{\mathcal{F}=1}^{(2)}(\tau) = 1 + \frac{\Delta_a^4}{4\Omega_a^4} e^{-\gamma_\sigma \tau}$, that can be understood as the two photons ω_ν and ω_σ arriving together. The presence of the laser thus makes them arrive at different times so that their coincidence is suppressed, but oscillations ensue as a result of this time redistribution. The effect can also be understood as beating due to detuning. More general spectral filtering brings us directly to the full two-photon spectrum. In presence of homodyning, i.e., the two-photon spectrum of the incoherent part alone, transforms the landscape of correlations from Fig. 2(f) to 3(b), i.e., the circle disappears. This is another proof of its origin from interferences between the squeezing, that remains and produces extreme bunching (cf. the scale), and coherence. The result is similar for the squeezed cavity, i.e., with $\Omega_a = 0$, but without the side leapfrogs, the central cross and the antibunching around the real peak (not shown). The general two-photon spectrum can be obtained analytically (for both the two-level system and the squeezed cavity,

both at and out-of resonance, with or without homodyning), but it is too voluminous to be replicated here. Excellent approximations can, however, be derived in the highly-detuned regime $\Delta_\sigma \gg \Omega_\sigma \gg \gamma_\sigma$, where emission drops due to the inefficient excitation of the system and thus enters in the Heitler regime, although the driving is taken much larger than decay. As a consequence, the main contribution for the emitted light is the coherent one. To leading order, the population of each sensor $\langle \varsigma_i^\dagger \varsigma_i \rangle$ —that both provide, from the sensor method, the spectral shape $S_\Gamma(\varpi)$ —recovers the spectral shape Eq. (5.7), featuring a diverging contribution at the origin that corresponds to the coherent δ peak, in addition to the symmetric side peaks, which are also revealed as not Lorentzian:

$$S_\Gamma(\varpi) = \frac{\epsilon^2 \Omega_\sigma^2}{\Delta_\sigma^4} \frac{1}{\varpi^2} + \frac{2\epsilon^2 \Omega_\sigma^4}{\Gamma \Delta_\sigma^6} \frac{\Gamma + 2\gamma_\sigma + \Gamma \varpi^2}{(1 - \varpi^2)^2} + \text{higher orders}. \quad (6.2)$$

The two-photon correlation spectrum is similarly obtained in both cases as:

$$g_\Gamma^{(2)}(\varpi_1, \varpi_2) = \frac{(\varpi_1^2 + \varpi_1 + \varpi_2^2 + \varpi_2)^2}{(\varpi_1 + \varpi_2)^2 (\varpi_1 + 1)^2 (\varpi_2 + 1)^2} + \text{higher orders}. \quad (6.3)$$

This surprisingly compact expression gives an excellent qualitative account of the detuned resonance fluorescence landscape shown in Fig. 2(f), with divergences and exact zeros that capture the resonances, which get tamed by the higher-order corrections as is the case for populations with Eq. (6.2). From the analysis of the zeros of both the numerator and denominator of this expression, we can thus locate the main features of the two-photon spectrum. Minima correspond to antibunching. They are found by setting the numerator of Eq. (6.3) to zero, which, rewriting the equation as

$$\left(\varpi_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\varpi_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} \quad (6.4)$$

is that of a circle centered at $\varpi_1 = \varpi_2 = -1/2$ and with radius $\sqrt{2}/2$. This not only gives the most compelling explanation for the circle of antibunching—as a two-mode interference between squeezing and coherence—it also shows that it is, indeed, an exact circle. Bunching maxima are actually divergences to leading order, and located at the condition that vanish the denominator, i.e.,

$$\varpi_1 = -1, \quad \varpi_2 = -1 \quad \text{and} \quad \varpi_1 + \varpi_2 = 0 \quad (6.5)$$

producing the three main bunching lines of detuned resonance fluorescence, which make a right-angled triangle. Additional maxima can be found looking for the zeros of higher orders (less pronounced in the plot). These are at

$$\varpi_1 = 1, \quad \varpi_2 = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \varpi_1 + \varpi_2 = \pm 1. \quad (6.6)$$

The horizontal and vertical correlations now concern the real peak, which is much less correlated than its virtual counterpart. The antidiagonal lines are the other leapfrog processes. All these lines, along with the circle, are plotted in Fig. 2(c) as a backbone for the two-photon correlation spectrum. The decomposition of the 2PS into its interference terms, using Eqs. (4.17), leads to:

$$\mathcal{I}_0 \approx \frac{\varpi_1^2 \varpi_2^2 (2 + \varpi_1 + \varpi_2)^2}{(\varpi_1 + \varpi_2)^2 (\varpi_1 + 1)^2 (\varpi_2 + 1)^2}, \quad (6.7a)$$

$$\mathcal{I}_1 \approx 0, \quad (6.7b)$$

$$\mathcal{I}_2 \approx -\frac{2\varpi_1 \varpi_2 (2 + \varpi_1 + \varpi_2)}{(\varpi_1 + \varpi_2)(\varpi_1 + 1)(\varpi_2 + 1)}. \quad (6.7c)$$

This reveals that, furthermore

$$\mathcal{I}_0 = (\mathcal{I}_2/2)^2 \quad (6.8)$$

which, from Eq. (4.14), provides $g_\Gamma^{(2)}$ as a function of the squeezing component alone:

$$g_\Gamma^{(2)} = \left(1 + \frac{\mathcal{I}_2}{2}\right)^2. \quad (6.9)$$

This relationship holds when the coherent fraction dominates over the incoherent, or quantum, fraction, with also phase-matching between them, in which case, squeezing can be related to photon fluctuations [37,83]. This is the case for instance in Eqs. (4.18) when $\phi_1 + \phi_2 - \vartheta_{12} = 0$ or π . This is also the case in the Heitler regime where the coherent fraction overtakes the signal [16,35], including in presence of filtering [55]. This relationship is the chief reason why squeezing has been more difficult to observe than antibunching [84]. In more general situations, in particular when \mathcal{I}_1 is nonzero, there are deviations from this ideal. The exact numerical results of \mathcal{I}_i for resonance fluorescence are shown in Fig. 2(g–o). The rightmost column of the detuned Heitler regime is well approximated by Eqs. (6.7) with, in particular, $\mathcal{I}_1 \approx 0$ (the darker area means a negative sign for the plotted quantity) and \mathcal{I}_0 and \mathcal{I}_2 having the redundant appearance from Eq. (6.8). The squeezing component changes sign on its various domains, as shown in the figure. The condition that produces the circle of exact antibunching leads to

$$\mathcal{I}_0 \approx 1, \quad \mathcal{I}_1 \approx 0, \quad \mathcal{I}_2 \approx -2, \quad (6.10)$$

which are the same as those for two-photon suppression from destructive interferences between the squeezing and coherent component, but here occurring at the two-photon (with two different frequencies) level. Since $\mathcal{I}_2 < 0$ for this to occur, this happens in the four triangles that corner the circle in Fig. 2(o). The right-angled triangle is also interesting. Its lines originate from \mathcal{I}_0 , like the leapfrog processes at resonance. They indeed lie at the frontier of \mathcal{I}_2 changing sign, as can be seen in Fig. 2(o) where they match the dotted lines where $\mathcal{I}_2 = 0$, although it is large (in absolute value) on both sides. The antidiagonal line corresponds to the central leapfrog line. The two new lines that appear, horizontal and vertical, betray the virtual character of the peak, which remains correlated, at this *pinned* frequency (this is the novelty as compared to other leapfrog photons), with all the other photons, at all the frequencies, including the real photon from the other peak, in which case one realizes the heralded two-photon scheme [68,81,82]. It is noteworthy that not only the circle, but also the vertical and horizontal lines disappear with homodyning (cf. Fig. 3(b)), which suggests that the anomalous correlator \mathcal{I}_1 plays an important role in the constitution of these “anomalous” lines, which therefore demand further attention, that is beyond the scope of our current discussion. In contrast, in the first column of Fig. 2, i.e., at resonance, one has the opposite situation where $\mathcal{I}_0 \gg \mathcal{I}_2$ and, furthermore, $\mathcal{I}_0 < 0$ in the two diagonal quadrants, which contain the spectral peaks (with a meticulous exclusion of the leapfrogs). This signals the non-Gaussian, i.e., Fock, or multiphoton emission, character of both the leapfrogs which have no squeezing associated to their constitution, and of the side peaks, which have the characteristic \mathcal{I}_0 of antibunching dominated by the fluctuations of the incoherent emission. The second column as the system transits from one case to the other shows the “evaporation” of the negative domain in \mathcal{I}_0 , which reduces to a tiny islet around the real peak only at high detuning, as well as the emergence and shaping of squeezing in \mathcal{I}_2 . It also shows the role of the anomalous correlator \mathcal{I}_1 in bridging between these two cases, being close to negligible in the other limits.

This achieves our description of the two-photon landscape of resonance fluorescence. All the features have been explained. There is a rich combination of various mechanisms, from multiphoton emission to multiphoton interferences, being realized in different regions of phase space where they can be isolated and exploited. We have largely focused on zero time-delay, but one could similarly consider the time dynamics of this physics, as we did in Ref. [82] where, cross-correlating the side peaks of detuned resonance fluorescence with or without homodyning the coherent peak, we observed a considerable transformation and enhancement of the correlation functions. Clearly, the problem is far from being exhausted. Also it should be clarified that although at the two-photon level, the physics is captured by two-mode squeezing, the broader problem including higher photon numbers goes much beyond this vantage point. One should not make the same mistake with two-photon spectra as has been made with single-photon ones, i.e., assuming that the picture is now complete. This might be the case for the squeezed cavity, since it only involves Gaussian states and thus is fully described through its two-photon correlators, higher-order ones being functions of those. But the two-level system gives rise to non-Gaussian

states, and so, the three-photon spectrum (and others of higher orders) are most certainly providing as radical changes as compared to the two-photon case than the two-photon case does to the single-photon one. Some of this higher-order physics does in fact indeed transpire in two-photon observables. In the next Section, we give a brief overview of a few alternative quantifiers of two-photon emission. There, one will get a chance to sight unaccounted-for phenomena.

7. Violation of Inequalities

The above results invite one to seek new regimes of strongly-correlated quantum emission, away from the spectral peaks. There is much to prospect for, and various regions (photons of different frequencies) provide us with different types of light. To highlight this point, we compute various quantifiers of nonclassical correlations, which can be applied to frequency-filtered photons [85]. We consider here the case of highly-detuned resonance fluorescence, since it was not previously considered in this context, and for being both a clean and fruitful source of correlations. We also add a new quantifier for two-mode squeezing, given the emphasis we have given to its role, also clarifying that while we have compellingly established the importance of squeezing in the broad phenomenology, we are far from having exhausted the topic. Figure 4(a) shows the violation of Cauchy-Schwarz inequalities when $R > 1$ where

$$R \equiv [g_{12}^{(2)}]^2 / [g_{11}^{(2)} g_{22}^{(2)}], \quad (7.1)$$

while panel (b) shows the violation of Bell's inequalities when $B > 2$ where, this time:

$$B \equiv \sqrt{2} \left| \frac{\langle s_1^\dagger s_1^2 \rangle + \langle s_2^\dagger s_2^2 \rangle - 4 \langle s_1^\dagger s_2^\dagger s_2 s_1 \rangle - \langle s_1^2 s_2^2 \rangle - \langle s_2^2 s_1^2 \rangle}{\langle s_1^2 s_1^2 \rangle + \langle s_2^2 s_2^2 \rangle + 2 \langle s_1^\dagger s_2^\dagger s_2 s_1 \rangle} \right|. \quad (7.2)$$

Panel (c) shows two-mode squeezing, which is present if and only if $S > 1$, where [86]:

$$S \equiv \frac{|\langle s_1^2 s_2^2 \rangle - \langle s_1 s_2 \rangle^2|}{\langle s_1^\dagger s_2^\dagger s_2 s_1 \rangle - |\langle s_1 \rangle \langle s_2 \rangle|^2}. \quad (7.3)$$

All these quantities are plotted in Fig. 4. From the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, one can see again the region of no-coincidence emission, where the system stops emitting at the two-photon level, which is the black circle. This quantity might be even more suitable to identify the region of no two-photon emission, being a more properly normalized version of two-photon correlations. It generalizes to two-photon emission the spectral line elimination via quantum interferences in spontaneous emission [87]. The green regions show nonclassical emission. Since the main diagonal is white, it means that the emission at any frequency from the spectrum is classical, which is also the case at resonance [85]. Both the main leapfrog and photons involving the virtual peak are strongly quantum correlated, and are likely valuable resources for quantum emitters of a new type. The Bell inequality is, interestingly, of a quite different character, being mainly attached to the main leapfrog (a bit as well to the circle of no-emission, surprisingly) where, unlike other quantifiers that behave more like resonances, it spreads and increases as one gets away from the triplet. Those are features that we cannot currently explain. Finally, Panel (c) which indicates two-mode squeezing is probably the most interesting as it first confirms that this is a feature to be found almost everywhere in detuned resonance fluorescence, except in the vicinity of the real peaks. More interestingly, however, new lines whose slope betray other photon combinations ($2\varpi_1 + \varpi_2 = k$ and $\varpi_1 + 2\varpi_2 = k$ where $k = -1$ or 0) reveal that there is rich additional physics that we have not yet touched upon, possibly involving squeezed correlations of higher photon numbers. Even at the qualitative level of explaining the basic but strong features that shape the landscape, we find evidence of more complicated processes inherited from beyond two-photon physics. Some of them have been discussed through $g^{(n)}$ correlators at resonance [67]. The features not yet accounted for from the quantifiers discussed in this Section are reported in Fig. 3(c) as thin lines, requiring new physics. In its pursuit, we could indeed, using the same approach and techniques, but computing other observables, characterize other types

of correlations, such as three-mode squeezing, other types of entanglement, quadrature-based tripartite inseparability [88,89], etc. It is clear that there remains much to explore, understand and turn into devices, even with the simplest problem of quantum optics, while the same approach can be applied to more complicated systems, from cosmic radiation to atoms and molecules passing by condensed matter and other types of quantum emitters.

Figure 4. Violations of (a) Cauchy and (b) Bell inequalities in highly-detuned resonance fluorescence, as well as presence of (c) two-mode squeezing. Filtering harvests correlations. Sight of new physics beyond that discussed in the text is also apparent. Parameters are the same as for Fig. 2(f).

8. Conclusion and Outlook

We have provided a detailed, and essentially analytical, picture of the two-photon physics of resonance fluorescence. Maybe the most important message is that this should be contemplated on its own, independently from one-photon observables, however ingrained is one's attachment to intensity, signal and photoluminescence spectra. This text was written at the invitation of the Royal Society to commemorate the Newton International Fellowship awarded to one of us (EdV, in 2009). It brings together various of EdV's research lines which started at this occasion with a theory of lasing that produced the Mollow triplet with coherence provided by the emitter itself as opposed to being brought from outside [80]. This led her to study in more details the coupling (and decoupling) of two-level systems [90] and how they develop and maintain correlations in the steady state [91], sustaining a rich span of different regimes interpolating between incoherent and coherent [92] from the interplay of quantum and dissipative light-matter interactions. The need to scrutinize as completely as possible photon correlations from such platforms led to the introduction of the frequency degree of freedom, this time as part of a Humboldt Fellowship. This provides the first pillar on which stands the edifice that explains the two-photon physics of resonance fluorescence (and a wealth of other problems in its wake): the theory of frequency-resolved multiphoton correlations [15,61]. The other pillar is the theory of quantum field admixtures [16]. Remarkably, while these have been pursued independently, they turn out to be naturally and deeply interconnected, besides, on what is possibly the simplest-possible nontrivial problem of quantum optics: the coherently driven two-level system. We believe that this betrays the extremely fundamental and universal character of these concepts. The other Authors of this text, as we are sure would also our past collaborators on these topics, concur that the surprisingly complex and rich phenomenology that is being revealed, far from exhausting or completing the description of the problem, is only making it even more mysterious and unfathomable. This evokes to us the aphorism of Newton himself:

«I seem to have been only like a boy playing on the sea-shore, and diverting myself in now and then finding a smoother pebble or a prettier shell than ordinary, whilst the great ocean of truth lay all undiscovered before me.»

While we have for brevity, simplicity and current experimental interest, focused on two-photon physics, the above approach is completely general and can, indeed inevitably will, be generalized to multiphoton correlations and n -mode squeezing. Spheres of antibunching [67] have already been spotted in three-photon correlation spectra and it is obvious that resonance fluorescence abounds with three-mode squeezing that remain to be characterized, measured and exploited. Among other compelling immediate continuations of this work, we can mention i) seizing additional control and tuneability of the correlations by externally adjusting the interferences with a laser [25], ii) using strongly-correlated two-photon spectral locations for quantum-spectroscopic applications [93] or iii) Purcell-enhancing them to realize new types of devices with high-purity and strong signal [74]. There are definitely still other and possibly even more exciting prospects. At any rate, it is clear that, although inconspicuous at the one-photon level, there is a rich and varied two-photon physics, which takes place everywhere.

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